

TRADITIONAL SILVOPASTORAL SYSTEMS AS SOIL CARBON RESERVOIRS IN SOUTHERN BRAZILIAN ARAUCARIA FORESTS ¹

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Abstract: Traditional silvopastoral systems (TSS) are present in several regions worldwide and play a key role in biodiversity conservation and in reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from livestock systems. This study aimed to quantify soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks in *caívas*, a TSS developed in remnants of the Araucaria Forest in southern Brazil. Two *caíva* areas were selected, and SOC was measured down to 1 meter depth, using six soil layers (0–5, 5–10, 10–20, 20–40, 40–60, and 60–100 cm) to enable accurate carbon stock (CStock) estimates across the soil profile. Results showed a significant effect of depth on CStock, with higher carbon accumulation in deeper layers. The mean SOC stock up to 1 meter was 324 Mg·ha⁻¹, indicating that *caívas* hold substantial potential as nature-based solutions for climate change mitigation in livestock-dominated landscapes in southern Brazil.

Keywords: *Caíva*; Mixed Ombrophilous Forest; Climate change mitigation; Livestock.

Introduction

Caívas are traditional forest–livestock systems located in the state of Santa Catarina, Southern Brazil, in which the canopy of the Araucaria Forest is maintained in association with extraction of *erva-mate* (*Ilex paraguariensis*) and livestock production (Hanisch et al., 2022). These systems are considered highly resilient and play a significant role in promoting biodiversity conservation (Lacerda et al., 2020). The integration of native trees and pastures also presents considerable potential for carbon sequestration, thereby contributing to the mitigation of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from livestock production (Freitas et al., 2020).

It is well established that, in pasture-based systems, the soil compartment holds a substantial capacity for carbon sequestration and long-term storage, being regarded as one of the largest carbon sinks on the planet (FAO, 2019). The presence of trees—through root system diversity and continuous litter input—further enhances the incorporation and

accumulation of soil organic carbon (SOC), strengthening the role of these systems in mitigating GHG emissions (Aryal et al., 2022).

In *caívas*, high levels of soil organic matter have been observed, averaging over 4% in the 0–10 cm layer (Hanisch et al., 2022), likely due to the presence of perennial pastures, abundant litterfall, and shading from tree canopies. Considering that, in most soils, approximately 75–90% of total soil organic carbon (SOC) is stored in the upper 1 m of the soil profile (Weil & Brady, 2017), this study aimed to conduct an exploratory analysis to estimate the total SOC stock in *caíva* areas. The objective is to generate data that support the recognition of *caívas* as effective strategies for reducing GHG emissions from livestock systems and to provide scientific evidence to justify the inclusion of these systems in environmental service payment schemes that benefit the farmers who conserve them.

Material and Methods

Soil samples were collected in two areas of *caívas* (26°27'34"S; 50°17'39"W and 26°13'23"S; 50°27'7"W) which shared a Cfb climate, Oxisols, and over 80 years of traditional *caíva* use with dairy cattle farming. In each area, two trenches measuring 1×1×1m were excavated, and soil samples were collected from both sides of each trench, totaling four replicates per site (Figure 1). The soil was sampled at six depth intervals: 0–5, 5–10, 10–20, 20–40, 40–60, and 60–100 cm, following the recommendations of FAO (2019) for accurate total SOC stock estimates across the profile. Soil bulk density was determined using undisturbed samples collected with volumetric rings at the center of each depth layer. Smaller rings (~73 cm³) were used for the 0–5 and 5–10 cm layers, and larger rings (~205 cm³) for deeper layers. After oven-drying at 105 °C for 48 hours, bulk density (g/cm³) was calculated as the ratio between dry mass and sample volume (EMBRAPA, 2017).

Data analysis was performed using R software (R Core Team, 2023). A two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to evaluate the effects of “Site” and “Depth” and their interaction on C stock and soil density. Tukey’s HSD test ($p < 0.05$) was applied to compare means across soil depths. Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) were calculated for each site and depth.

Results and Discussion

No statistically significant differences were observed in soil bulk density or soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks between the two *caíva* areas evaluated. Similarly, no significant interaction was found between site and soil depth for either variable. However, soil depth had a pronounced effect on both parameters (Table 1). The 0–10 cm layer exhibited the highest bulk density, which can likely be attributed to continuous livestock trampling throughout the year. Nonetheless, the measured values did not reach thresholds associated with detrimental soil compaction, suggesting that the traditional management practices in these systems may help preserve soil structure.

Table 1. Soil bulk density and soil organic carbon stock in *caíva* areas at six different depths. Canoinhas and Major Vieira cities, Santa Catarina State, Brazil. 2023.

Deep (cm)	Soil bulk Density (g.m ³)		Carbon stock (Mg.ha ⁻¹)	
	mean	sd	mean	sd
0-5	1.13 a	0.12	32.54 c	8.17
5-10	1.07 a	0.06	26.14 c	3.68
10-20	0.97 b	0.09	44.25 bc	4.9
20-40	1.01 b	0.16	79.58 a	26.1
40-60	0.98 b	0.08	55.71 b	12.89
60-100	1.03 b	0.07	98.28 a	18.75

Médias seguidas por letras iguais, nas colunas, não diferem entre si pelo Teste de Tukey ($p>0.05$)

Soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks increased with depth, although more than 50% of the total estimated stock — 326 Mg·ha⁻¹ down to 1 m — was concentrated in the upper 40 cm of the soil profile. Notably, the 60–100 cm layer accounted for nearly 30% of the total SOC, highlighting the importance of deeper soil layers in long-term carbon storage. These results underscore the role of *caívas* as traditional silvopastoral systems with substantial potential for deep soil carbon sequestration.

The SOC stocks observed in the *caívas* were particularly noteworthy, exceeding values reported for secondary forests in the Atlantic Forest biome when assessed at equivalent depths (Guerrini et al., 2024). This outcome reinforces the synergistic benefits derived from the integration of trees and pastures in silvopastoral systems, particularly regarding their capacity for carbon sequestration (Morales-Ruiz et al., 2025). Aryal et al. (2022) reported positive correlations between aboveground tree biomass, fine root biomass, and SOC concentrations, indicating that tree presence directly contributes to enhanced carbon storage in soils.

Conclusões

The results demonstrated that soil carbon distribution varied across depth intervals, with a total mean stock of $324 \text{ Mg} \cdot \text{ha}^{-1}$ down to 1 m. More than half of this total was concentrated in the upper 40 cm of the soil. These findings confirm that *caívas* function as substantial soil carbon reservoirs, even under long-term grazing, with cattle presence spanning nearly a century. Such insights enhance the understanding of carbon dynamics in forest–livestock systems and may inform policy frameworks aimed at carbon mitigation and the recognition of traditional land-use systems as contributors to climate change adaptation strategies.

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